

Science of Voice Culture

Dr. Surekha Murlidharrao Joshi

Associate Prof & Head of dept. (music) KSK College, Beed (M.S.)

Corresponding author- Dr. Surekha Murlidharrao Joshi

Email-surekharatnaparkhi8@gmail.com

Abstract:

The first essential to one beginning the study of voice culture is an appreciation of the real significance of voice development .voice is a natural reporter of the conditions, emotions, thoughts, and purposes (character and states or conditions) of the individual. The ring of true culture in the voice is that perfect modulation of tone and movement which, without self-consciousness, communicates exactly the meaning and purpose which impel the utterances of the speaker. It is almost impossible for any person to cultivate vocal expression to the best advantage without an intelligent and sympathetic teacher; he lacks the perspective upon himself which is necessary in order to correct his individual faults and draw out his most effective powers.

An ideal tone is one that is balanced (between all resonating cavities), free flowing (no tensions or restrictions), resonant (with all overtones present and a ring), pure (The timbre is not contrived) and is supported by good and steady breath pressure .It is also defined by good clean articulation.

Although we do not hear own voices as others do. It is a good practice to hear and analyze our own tone and try to find the best tonal balance which is repeatable and freedom-inducing. One needs to carefully observe the sound one produces with the mind's eye ,how it feels and how it looks, in terms of vocal posture ,position of jaw ,tongue ,head, shoulders etc .A good resonance happens when the sound produced by the vocal folds is intensified by the air-filled cavities through which it passes .One can follow the practice of the rendering each note and play around with placement of altering the nature of tone to see what happens with each change .For example a tone a tone might be altered to make it more nasal, or more breathy or more centered With the right amount of experimentation, this will help the student find the right “ ring” or resonance in the tone.

A good exercise to help feel the resonating effect in various chambers is

- 1) Sit upright and perfect the posture before starting exercise.
- 2) Remember at no time , should you feel any tension, or constriction in throat, should the larynx rise up, or should extra air be pushed out to compensate for lack of reach or unevenness of tone .the breath should always be minimal and flow out steadily in a relaxed fashion.
- 3) Choose a note at the lower end of the spectrum and start to hum with it the following preparation. Breathe in like you are surprised, this will help to open the back of throat and raise the soft palate. This is very important position to take before starting to sing any phrase. Enlarging the cavity of the throat and lengthening the chamber in the mouth will help resonance occur more naturally.

- 4) Try to hum on the sound ‘ng’ as in sing. You will feel a strong buzzing sensation behind the nose and eyes. You can then transition this into a hum. The soft palate can be lifted up more to get a different placement. With proper breathing continue to do this exercise doing long resonant hum s.

Remember to not add any tension or extra pressure as you go up the scale. As you ascend the scale, you should feel more resonance in the head cavities. If you don't you can try to flex the soft palate more and try to imagine saying the sound ‘ooo’ as in ‘soup’. This will help place the tone forward and stronger. Remember to not clench your jaw or throat. The tongue should always be forward in its resting place, the tip should be touching the bottom front teeth. Sometimes, you can feel your teeth rattling or nose buzz as you hum on higher pitches .remember to also keep you rib-cage expanded as you breathe.

Once this is done, you can try the same exercise and alternate between a hum and various vowels .Singing should always feel like a hum, there should be no shouting or tension. Doing this exercise would be very helpful to get idea of how a good tone should sound.

Personal supervision and direction of his efforts which will allow his mind to be constantly occupied with thoughts and principles, and relieve him of all temptation to watch his own performances as such But it is necessary that the student should have a simple and logical basis for practice, however great may become the variety of its application. That the voice is naturally expressive is shown in the fact that even where there is no possible suggestion of cultivation we instinctively read the broad outlines of meaning and feeling in the tones and inflections of the voice. May it not therefore be possible that a finer culture will reveal all the subtle shades of thought and feeling, and a more discriminating judgment be able to detect these, just as the ethnologist will reconstruct from some crude relic the history of an earlier

civilization? We must remember, too, that first of all the voice is a vital instrument. The physical condition affects most noticeably the quality, strength, and movement of the voice. Hence we see that physical health is essential to a good voice, and the proper use of the voice is itself one of the most invigorating exercises that can be practiced. All the vital organs are called into healthful action through this extraordinary manipulation of the breath, and the nervous system, both vitally and emotionally, receives invigoration. In the beginning, therefore, such vital conditions as are essential to the production of tone should be considered. First, a standing position, in which the vital organs are well sustained, is essential. One cannot even breathe properly unless one stands well. The weight should be mainly upon the balls of the feet, and the crown of the head so positively elevated as to secure the erectness of the spinal column. This will involve the proper elevation of the chest, the essential freedom of respiration, and the right sustaining tension of the abdominal muscles.

Role of Lips, Teeth and Throat while Singing.

Certainly, for us to sing better, we not only need to know how to protect our voice we also need to understand the various common singing problems or habits that we may have, as well as how to avoid them!

- The **more the lips move** the better the voice
- If you **open the mouth and teeth** your voice is still better
- Voice is the best when you sing with a **smiling face**
- To improve the voice power, flicker a candle kept at a 5 feet distance by blowing
- Produce bouncy and light 'ssss' sounds with our breath, that would be extremely useful to us whenever we need to sing fast songs (like Breathless sung by Shankar Mahadevan)
- Keep **Our Neck, Jaw and Face Relaxed** During Singing
- If you are singing in a standing position, bend one of your knees.
- Look into the mirror while you sing. Ensure you have a smiling face, You are **not doing neck breathing or shoulder breathing.**

Aging and Voice Production

Children – For kids the vocal ligament is incomplete. So their range is relatively narrow. You should never force a kid to improve/increase his/her pitch. Doing so may damage his/her vocal ligaments due to over strain. Kids should be left to sing at their own most comfortable level of pitch.

Adolescence–The voice of girls are not much affected during adolescence. But for boys, pitch drops by one octave as their vocal chords starts getting thicker during this age. Voice tend to become a base voice. This is a temporary phase. They

can feel the astonishing change in their voice after this phase.

Ladies during Menopause– Estrogen production goes down. This influences their voice slightly. The pitch goes down. This was demonstrated by the great singer P. Leela's voice during her young age and old age. Again this is different on a case to case basis. The great singer S. Janaki's voice remains almost the same even at this age!

Generally the voice is best during the middle of a menstrual cycle for a woman. It is always advised to choose this time frame for professional recordings or to give public concerts, when the voice is more sweet and powerful. It is not advisable to sing or give a concert just 3-4 days before your monthly menstrual cycle. The voice gradually improves after the period. For a Male the pitch drops slightly after 60 years. The breath control and the power of singing also fall down. In a very old age- say after 75, the pitch raises for both male and female.

Vocal Hygiene

- One of the major **"Good Food for Good Singing" is actually a liquid, and it is called Water.** The most essential ingredient for a honey dipped voice is the intake of adequate water. Water should be neither too hot nor too cold. It should be lukewarm. There is not limit for drinking water as it improves the human system in other ways also. But make sure that your urine should be colourless.
- Never steam or inhale for improving vocal cords.
- Bathroom singing is very good as the air in the bathroom contains lot of humidity.
- If possible stand in neck deep water and do the Saadhakam.

A to Z Singing Tips

- **A = Airflow.**
Never hold your breath while singing. The airflow is what creates and carries your vocal tone, so keep it flowing. Avoid Clavicular Breathing and Belly Breathing - instead; learn the proper way to breathe for singing, called diaphragmatic breathing. Fill the lower portion of your lungs as if you had an inner tube around your waist that you were evenly filling.
- **B = Breathing**
Properly for singing requires the shoulders to remain down and relaxed, not rise with the breath intake. A singer will gain power to their voice by strengthening the muscles in their ribcage and back.
- **C = Communicate**
The music's message. During performance it is very important to communicate the message of the song. If you make a "mistake" don't point it out to your audience. It is most likely they did not even notice.

- **D = Diaphragmatic**
Support Develop the strength and coordination of the diaphragm and become a pro at controlling the speed of the airflow released, the quantity of the airflow released and the consistency of the airflow released.
- **E = Elasticity**
Of the Vocal Folds the vocal tone is created as airflow bursts through the cleft of the vocal cords causing them to vibrate/oscillate. The vocal folds can lose elasticity due to misuse, lack of use and/or increase of age. Be sure to train your voice with vocal exercises on a regular basis to keep your voice in shape.
- **F = Free your natural voice.**
Don't be a slave to any music style — even your favorite one. Learn to sing with your full and natural voice by developing your vocal strength and coordination. Then add stylistic nuances to achieve any singing style you desire.
- **G = Guessing Games.**
Never guess the pitch you are about to sing. Hear the note in your head before you open your mouth.
- **H = High notes**
Require consistent and steady airflow. Many students tend to hold their breath as they sing higher. Let the air flow. Try increasing your airflow and gauge your result.
- **I = Increase**
You're breathing capacity and control by doing breathing exercises every day. Be sure to avoid patterned breathing. Singers must negotiate phrase lengths of all different sizes, so it is important to be versatile.
- **J = Jumping Jacks.**
If you are having trouble getting your body completely involved with singing, try doing some cardiovascular activities, like jumping jacks, for a few minutes before getting started again. Sometimes your instrument simply needs an airflow wake-up call.
- **K = Know your limits.**
Don't sing too high or too low. Don't sing to the point of vocal fatigue. Never strain or push your voice. Doing so will not result in a higher or lower singing range, or a stronger voice, only a voice that has suffered undue stress.
- **L = Low notes**
Are often sung with too much airflow Try decreasing your airflow to achieve a more natural, more relaxed tone.
- **M = Mirror.**
Training in front of a mirror can help a singer discover many things about their instrument, as well as confirm that other actions are being done correctly. Be sure to rely on a mirror during vocal training, but be able to leave the mirror to face an audience.
- **N = Never**
Sing if it hurts to swallow.
- **O = Open**
Your mouth wider nine times out of ten this will help you achieve a stronger, more defined vocal tone.
- **P = Prepare**
Your instrument before singing Singers are very much like athletes. Take care of your body/instrument by stretching out the vocal muscles and relieving the body of unnecessary tension before singing.
- **Q = Quit**
Quit smoking. Quit talking too loudly. Quit talking too much.
- **R = Raise the Soft Palate.**
Creating a larger space inside your mouth by raising the soft palate, or fleshy part of the back of our throat, helps achieve a deeper more well-rounded singing tone.
- **S = Sing**
Through the vocal breaks if you do not teach the muscles the necessary actions to sing through the trouble spots, success will never be achieved. Sing through it, sing through it again, and again....
- **T = Tone Placement.**
Learning the facts about tone placement and resonance make a huge difference in the abilities of a singer, In simple terms, a singer has numerous body cavities (nasal cavity, chest cavity, etc.) and amplifiers (bones, ligaments, etc.) that act as resonators. Focusing the vocal tone through the proper resonating chamber with the proper support is important with regard to controlling and developing your personal sound.
- **U = Unique Voice**
Under Construction Remember that your voice has its own unique fingerprint and is constantly changing with our actions, environment, health habits, etc. With this in mind, listen to your own voice often and use vocal training tools to keep your voice on the right track.
- **V = Vibrato.**
Vibrato is a natural or forced fluctuation of a singing tone. Do not concentrate on learning how to sing with vibrato. Instead, concentrate on the basic foundations of singing, breathing and support. When the proper coordination is achieved, vibrato will occur naturally.
- **W = Water. Water.**
Water Drink room temperature water as often as you can to keep your voice organ hydrated. If you only have cold or hot water available, swish it around in your mouth for a moment. This

action will keep your voice organ from being startled or stressed by different temperatures.

- **Y = You**

Can Sing with Impact! Exercise your voice daily with contemporary voice lesson products. Don't Just Sing when You Can Sing with Impact!

- **Z = ZZZZZZZ.**

Be sure to get your rest. If you are tired, your voice will show it. A tired body/instrument will not allow you to produce your best possible sound.

References:

1. Voice culture By- S.A.K. Turka (Publisher- Indian musicological society 1978)
2. Expressive voice culture
3. Jessie Eldridge Southwick.
4. Sangeet Kala vihair